

TO THE INTERNATIONAL SELF OF EMBROIDERY CHARACTERISTICS

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Summary. The author explains in this article examples of interethnic features of embroidery. It also contains tips on how to apply a wide variety of applications in architecture and in decorating objects.

Keywords and concepts: custom, feature, element, pattern, leaf, suzane, whip, leaf, mirror, teapot, basil, palak.

Each nation has its own customs and characteristics. For example, Ukrainian folk motifs show more sunflowers, birds, wheat and other things, while Kyrgyz and Kazakh motifs depict horned animals and their horns, grasses. Tajik folk motifs include tulips, almonds, and various flowers; Turkmen folk motifs often depict goat's head, grape trunks, and birds, while typical elements of Uzbek folk motifs include leaves, flowers, buds, buds, tulips, peppers, pomegranates, pomegranate leaves, pears, multi-leafed flowers, etc.

Appliqué is Latin for pasting and means decorating with tissue paper and other sewing. Appliqué is a special type of embroidery, which has its own technology. A piece of colored fabric, leather, etc. is pinned to the main fabric, and the circumference is stitched. Drawing stitches are often used in appliqué. This type of embroidery is well developed in Uzbekistan. Currently, children's coats, shirts, and hats are often embroidered with various bird, fruit, flower, and animal images in the appliqué method. In some cases, women's clothes are decorated in this way. The application method is widely used in architecture and decoration of an object.

The art of embroidery was widespread in Central Asia, and every woman in the family had to know how to embroider. Therefore, each family made their own kirpech, sozana, dorpech, glass bag, tea bag, etc. There are many types of decorative items, such as sozana, kirpech, bedclothes, mirror bag, tea bag, zardevor, palak, guokorpa, dorpech, bugjoma, curtain, belt, takyapush (to be covered on the pillow), hat, shirt, tablecloth, purse, joynamaz, bag, nimcha, mahsi-kavush, bag and others are sewn on fabrics with artistic taste. Later, satin and silk were sewn on velvet.

Joynamaz is a mat that is placed on the ground and prayed on. It is used by those who believe in the religion of Islam. It is imagined as a factor that separates a person from this world during prayer. Joynamaz is made of various fabrics, its three sides are sewn in the form of a mihrab, and it is used in mosques, madrasas and houses. It comes in different sizes. Other things can be used to avoid prayer. For example, from chapon, kiikcha, sholcha, etc., because they are considered pure from a religious point of view. Joynamoz is beautifully decorated with embroidery.

Zardevor is a home appliance. It is an art piece decorated with silk, velvet, satin embroidery. Zardevor is hung on the house, shaft or wall of the newly married bride in Uzbek and Tajik cultures. It has the size of a thread or silk, its width is 40-70 cm, and it is sewn to fit the wall of the intended house.

Palak is one of the largest and most expensive decorative items hung on walls. The palak depicts the sky and the full moon. In ancient times, it was made with white and gray embroidery. It differs from sozana by the size of its flowers and the fact that the floor is covered with embroidery. In the center of the palak, a large moon image is embroidered with red crimson, pink silk, and pepper elements are used around it, making it very beautiful. Up to forty moons can be depicted in Palak. Therefore, we know that six-month palak, twelve-month palak, and even forty-month palak for big houses were made depending on the number of the month. The months are depicted in several different colors. Famous embroiderers have sometimes shown their skills by decorating the moon with wonderful patterns. If the inside of the moon is represented in a solid color, it is called aypalak, if it is patterned, it is called gulpanak, etc. In recent times, great importance is attached to sewing the palak by hand.

Kirpech - kirpush, an art piece that is used to decorate the house over the clothes hung on the rack or hung on the wall in vertical spaces. Kirpech embroidery is sewn by hand or by machine. The kirpech is hand-embroidered. It protects clothes from dust and decorates the house. Usually, it is called kirpechpalak, which is sewn like a palak. This type is also widely used.

Sozana is also known as Sozana in Persian. It means sewn with a needle. Sozana is an art piece made by embroidery on fabric and hung on the wall to decorate the room. It is made by embroidery on satin, velvet, silk and other fabrics. It has a unique artistic look. The color of the fabric is used as a background for embroidery. Therefore it is different from palak. Sozana was in every household, because every girl prepared sozana for herself before marriage. Sozana is considered as dowry of brides.

In the poor family, the sozana was sewn from malla, white gray, and in the rich ones, from silk and velvet. Plant-like patterns are used in the composition for the sozana. A circular flower is often sewn in the middle of the sozana, and the surroundings are decorated with floral Islamic motifs. Sozana sewing has been developed for a very long time, sozanas have not been preserved until the 19th century. There are only examples of sozana types from Samarkand, Boysun, Bukhara, Nurota, Fergana, Oratepa, Shahrisabz, Tashkent and other places of the 19th century. This type of art has long been widespread, especially in the regions of Uzbekistan and Tajikistan. Since the 40s of the 20th century, sozana has been sewn by machine.

Cheyshab - Persian-Tajik ruyjo - means night tent. A bed sheet is mainly placed on the bed to hold it in place and cover it while lying down. The bed sheet is made of white silk with little embroidery, satin, silk, velvet, etc. Currently, it is also used as an art object like a sozana.

Pupils' interest in applied art was thoroughly studied and a system of activities aimed at increasing their interest was developed (Fig. 1).

Readers will learn about the fact that embroidery is the basis of Uzbek folk art, unique compositions of the ancient Eastern architectural art, ganch, wood carving and other types of applied art, which are famous all over the world for their beauty and elegance.

They learn the main principles of embroidery - harmony, proportion, color and the history of the methods and their importance. The traditions of embroidery (as well as

methods of teaching this type of art), in which natural luster of color, exquisite form, high examples of rich creative fantasy, acquire knowledge, skills and abilities.

Figure 1. A system of activities aimed at increasing students' interest in applied and artistic decorative arts

It is appropriate to increase the following recommendations in the development of students' interest in practical and artistic decorative arts:

- providing information on various methods of teaching practical and artistic decorative arts to students in the DTS, model curricula and programs of general education schools, on the development of effective ways of teaching;
- organization of training of professional teachers teaching applied and artistic decorative arts on the basis of information technologies;
- it is necessary to ensure the high level of various contests in visual and applied arts in the republic and the participation of students in them.

In general education schools, our national values serve as an important factor in the proper organization of the student's activities, the creative environment in the family, the upbringing of young people as true successors of the Uzbek folk art inherited from our ancestors, and the right direction in life.

After all, today it is no secret that the 21st century in which we live is a century dominated by intellectual wealth. Anyone who does not realize this fact in time, if the pursuit of intellectual wealth does not become the content of daily life for any nation and state, such a state will inevitably be left behind on the path of world development.

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